

CLASSROOM MANAGEMENT AND TEACHER'S MANNER

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ABSTRACT

In this article, we will discuss classroom management and how to build good relationships with students and engage them in the classroom.

There is no doubt that every teacher wants to be a fan teacher, cool teacher for their pupils and especially good specialized one in the area of their profession. In fact, teachers always have to start thinking of what is the best possible way being a right learner and keeping respect without disobeying for their pupils.

Then what is acceptable way?

In many cases, the main responsibility for controlling them lies with teachers well-experienced pedagogical method and organizational skills in class.

And now, we are going to propose vitally usable tips managing and organizing the classroom, as much as possible. Miraculously, we divide them in five parts and try to open the whole meaning with examples, of course.

Organizational skill.

Organizing strategies include planning, lesson design, time management and classroom management. Actually, organization means that pupils are in their proper place, at the proper time and know what's expected of them, undoubtedly, the teacher is ready with effective lessons.

If there is some pupils who are not in class on time due to lack of effective tardy policy, their education may suffer. Pupils with good organizational skills have the ability to create and maintain systems to keep track of information or materials.

Definitely, good organization can avoid unnecessary ineffectiveness both teachers and pupils. Planning your lesson mustn't be exactly for that day, you should prepare

weekly then you do not need spend most times for planning.

2. Classroom management.

Classroom management refers to the variety of skills and teaching techniques which helps to teachers keeping pupils organized, focused, and also orderly, academically productive during a class.

Deciding which techniques to use their lesson the most crucial one as every pupil and class is unique.

In this case, just imagine!!! You are a teacher who is standing in front of pupils the first day of a class. And of course, traditionally you start introducing yourself with adding your techniques styles, expectations and rules. It is a best way that telling them what you expect from them and what are your rules, orders what methods you use step by step during your teaching. Exactly, it helps to pupils mentally prepare for each stage of the lesson in their brain.

3. Warm-up activity.

It is important that, creative play helps pupil develop emotionally, physically, mentally and at last socially.

The first thing that the purpose of a warm up is to wake up them, you must take into consideration it.

Necessarily, active learning can increase experiencing, discovering, creativity are the most parts of creative play for them. During the games encourage them to ask questions and investigate their own ideas.

4. Handling noise in the classroom.

There is an issue that depends on keeping calm noisy environment in your classroom

It isn't always like plain sailing to handle the class orderly which all teachers have to face with it, in most cases.

The majority of teachers use shouting to make them quiet, it is all incorrect. Fortunately, your respect plays a crucial role in your teaching. So, you are not opera singer, you do not need to speak loudly fighting tone. Because you know that, some teenagers may have behavioral problems and they tend to be easily annoyed, irritated, at least, they may show their disrespect and refuse to obey .All in all your shouting against for yourself !

One the other side, it sends out a strong message to pupils about your behavior which you demonstrate, in turns. Instead of them address pupils individually name by name, not as a group.

5. Dealing with difficult pupils.

Dealing with difficult behavior is a part of every teacher's job in the area of their education.

When an incident of bad behavior occurs, please stay calm ,define right way from wrong, bring the misbehavior one close to you, try to understand and talk them privately.

Furthermore, emphasize problem-solving instead of punishment give a chance to respond them positively.

In addition to this, give more responsibility they should be under the work such as tasks, games or any activity then they do not have time to create noisy atmosphere and misbehave.

All things considered, punishing, arguing is not for skilled teacher

Eventually, you are not opponent, you are not rival to them, you are educator who lead them right way. Do not forget!!! You have a pedagogical skills, use them wisely.

Teachers have mission which they both educate and bring up the next generation who are moral and well-educated successors!!!

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